

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Beginqulova Shohsanam

IBN SINO SHE'RLARI JAMLANGAN (سینا ابن دیوان) "IBN SINO DEVONI) ASARI HAQIDA

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

